

Verified implementation of associative containers with iterators using threaded red-black trees (*Technical Report – Additional examples*)

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In a published paper [2] we address the verification of abstract data types (ADTs) implementing associative containers like maps and sets with fine-grained specifications for iterators, which allow for multiple readers and writers in client code. Our verified implementations are written in the verification-aware programming language Dafny. In that paper we introduce new methodological contributions in verifying heap-allocated data structures, such as separation between heap-based components and functional behavior, and fine-grained control of verification proofs. Additionally, we have implemented a library of associative containers in Dafny, including a verified implementation of threaded red-black trees with iterators. These contributions aim to reduce proof complexity in order to improve verification times, while maintaining proper encapsulation.

In this technical report we show the Dafny source code of a few additional examples that are referenced in [2], namely, the implementation of a Set ADT by using a previously verified map (`TreeMap`), and a function `Intersection` that computes the intersection of two ordered sets by using two iterators that traverse them.

1 Implementation of a set using a map

Here we present an outline of the implementation of a set using a map in a fully abstract way. We have implemented trait `TreeSet` using a field `treemap` of abstract type `TreeMap`. Only in the constructor a specific class name, `TreeMapImpl`, is mentioned to build a map object. We show below the required predicates `Valid` and `Model`, which rely on the corresponding predicates on `treemap`; the constructor, and the implementation of method `Add`.

The footprint is defined in terms of the footprint of `treemap` in a stratified way by defining function `ReprFamily`. In [1] you can find more details about the stratified representation applied to linear datatypes. The representation depth is that of `TreeMap` increased by three. Level 0 is the object itself. In level 1 the fields of the class are added, i.e., the `treemap` and the set `iterators`. In level 2 the iterators on `treemap` that implement the iterators on the set are added. In level 3 and above, all the objects that belong to the representation of `treemap` are added. These depend on the particular implementation `TreeMapImpl` we use in the constructor, but `TreeSetImpl` does not know anything about them.

```
1 class TreeSetIteratorImpl extends OrderedSetIterator { ...
2   const iter: OrderedMapIterator
3   ghost const parent: TreeSetImpl
4 }
5 class TreeSetImpl extends TreeSet { ...
6   const treemap: TreeMap
7   ghost var iterators: set<TreeSetIteratorImpl>
8
9   ghost function ReprFamily(n: nat): set<object>
10    decreases n
11    ensures n > 0 ==> ReprFamily(n) ≥ ReprFamily(n-1)
12    reads if n = 0 then {} else ReprFamily(n-1)
13    { if n = 0 then {this}
```

```

14     else if n = 1 then ReprFamily(0) + {treemap} + iterators
15     else if n = 2 then ReprFamily(1) + (set it ← iterators • it.iter)
16     else ReprFamily(2) + treemap.ReprFamily(n-3)
17 }
18 ghost predicate Valid() {
19   ReprDepth = treemap.ReprDepth + 3
20   ∧ (assert treemap.Repr() ≤ Repr(); true)
21   ∧ treemap.Valid()
22   ∧ this ∉ treemap.Repr()
23   ∧ iterators ∩ treemap.Repr() = {}
24   ∧ (∀ it ← iterators • it.parent = this)
25   ∧ (∀ it ← iterators • it.iter in treemap.Iterators())
26   ∧ (∀ it1 ← iterators, it2 ← iterators | it1 ≠ it2 • it1.iter ≠ it2.iter)
27 }
28 ghost function Model(): set<K>
29 { treemap.Model().Keys }
30
31 constructor() {
32   var treemap := new TreeMapImpl();
33   ReprDepth := treemap.ReprDepth + 3;
34   this.treemap := treemap;
35   iterators := {};
36 }
37
38 method Add(k: K)
39   ensures AddModel(k)
40   ensures AddIterators(k)
41 { treemap.Add(k, 0); }
42 }

```

2 Intersection of two ordered sets

We show here the code of method `Intersection` that given two ordered sets of integers, `s1` and `s2`, computes their intersection in set `su`. In order to do it in an efficient way, iterators `it1` and `it2` traverse respectively `s1` and `s2` in increasing order. Whenever the iterators point to the same integer, it is added to `su`. On the contrary, the iterator pointing to the smallest integer is advanced as ordered traversal guarantees that the integer does not belong to the other set. We omit all the allocation, freshness and validity properties. We also omit the details of the proofs, done by revealing the appropriate opaque predicates. Lemma `LoopInvariantImpliesIntersectionModel` proves that the invariant implies the postcondition when the loop ends.

```

1 method Intersection(s1: OrderedSet, s2: OrderedSet, su: OrderedSet)
2   requires IntersectionModelPre(s1, s2, su)
3   ensures IntersectionModel(s1, s2, su)
4 {
5   var it1: OrderedSetIterator := s1.First();
6   var it2: OrderedSetIterator := s2.First();
7
8   var it1HasPeek := it1.HasPeek();
9   var it2HasPeek := it2.HasPeek();
10
11   assert LoopInvariant(s1,old(s1.Model()),it1,s2,old(s2.Model()),it2,su)
12     by { reveal ... }
13
14   while it1HasPeek ∧ it2HasPeek
15     decreases LoopBound(s1, it1, s2, it2, su)
16     invariant it1HasPeek = it1.HasPeek?()
17     invariant it2HasPeek = it2.HasPeek?()
18     invariant LoopInvariant(s1,old(s1.Model()),it1,s2,old(s2.Model()),it2,su)
19   {
20     it1HasPeek, it2HasPeek :=
21       LoopBody(s1, old(s1.Model()), it1, s2, old(s2.Model()), it2, su);
22   }
23
24   LoopInvariantImpliesIntersectionModel(s1, it1, s2, it2, su);
25 }
26 }
27
28 opaque ghost predicate IntersectionModelPre(
29   s1: OrderedSet, s2: OrderedSet, su: OrderedSet )
30 { su.Model() = {} }

```

```

31
32 opaque twostate predicate IntersectionModel(
33   s1: OrderedSet, s2: OrderedSet, su: OrderedSet )
34 {  $\wedge$  s1.Model() = old(s1.Model())
35    $\wedge$  s2.Model() = old(s2.Model())
36    $\wedge$  su.Model() = s1.Model() * s2.Model()
37 }

1
2 opaque ghost predicate LoopInvariant(
3   s1: OrderedSet, s1Model: set<K>, it1: OrderedSetIterator,
4   s2: OrderedSet, s2Model: set<K>, it2: OrderedSetIterator,
5   su: OrderedSet )
6 {  $\wedge$  s1.Model() = s1Model
7    $\wedge$  s2.Model() = s2Model
8    $\wedge$  su.Model() = it1.Traversed() * it2.Traversed()
9    $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  a  $\leftarrow$  it1.Traversed(), b  $\leftarrow$  s2.Model() $\rightarrow$ it2.Traversed()  $\bullet$  a < b)
10   $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  a  $\leftarrow$  it2.Traversed(), b  $\leftarrow$  s1.Model() $\rightarrow$ it1.Traversed()  $\bullet$  a < b)
11 }
12
13 opaque ghost function LoopBound(
14   s1: OrderedSet, it1: OrderedSetIterator,
15   s2: OrderedSet, it2: OrderedSetIterator,
16   su: OrderedSet): nat
17 { (|s1.Model()| - |it1.Traversed()|) + (|s2.Model()| - |it2.Traversed()|) }
18
19
20 method LoopBody(
21   s1: OrderedSet, ghost s1Model: set<K>, it1: OrderedSetIterator,
22   s2: OrderedSet, ghost s2Model: set<K>, it2: OrderedSetIterator,
23   su: OrderedSet )
24   returns ( it1HasPeek: bool, it2HasPeek: bool)
25
26   requires it1.HasPeek?()
27   requires it2.HasPeek?()
28   requires LoopInvariant(s1, s1Model, it1, s2, s2Model, it2, su)
29
30   ensures it1HasPeek = it1.HasPeek?()
31   ensures it2HasPeek = it2.HasPeek?()
32   ensures LoopBound(s1, it1, s2, it2, su) < old(LoopBound(s1, it1, s2, it2, su))
33   ensures LoopInvariant(s1, s1Model, it1, s2, s2Model, it2, su)
34 {
35   var it1Peek := it1.Peek(); var it2Peek := it2.Peek();
36
37   if it1Peek = it2Peek {
38     su.Add(it1Peek);
39     it1.Next();
40     it2.Next();
41   }
42   else if it1Peek < it2Peek {
43     it1.Next();
44   }
45   else {
46     it2.Next();
47   }
48
49   it1HasPeek := it1.HasPeek(); it2HasPeek := it2.HasPeek();
50 }
51 }

```

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References

- [1] Blázquez, J., Montenegro, M., Segura, C.: Verification of mutable linear data structures and iterator-based algorithms in Dafny. *Journal of Logical and Algebraic Methods in Programming* **134**, 100875 (2023)

- [2] Blázquez, J., Montenegro, M., Segura, C.: Verified implementation of associative containers with iterators using threaded red-black trees. In: Proceedings of 20th International Conference on Integrated Formal Methods (iFM 2025). Springer (2025)